

S2 – Supplementary Material - Sociometric Badge Settings

3.1.2669GEDIIISettings

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Configuration name	3.1.2669GEDIIISettings
Firmware version	3.1.2669

Accelerometer

Interval (in milliseconds) to read accelerometer values	<input type="range"/>	50ms
Interval (in milliseconds) to store accelerometer features	<input type="range"/>	100ms

Infrared

Interval to send IR beacon (used for IR detections)	<input type="range"/>	1000ms
Random value to +- IR beacon interval, e.g. value of 100 means actual detections happen (interval +- 100 ms)	<input type="range"/>	100ms
Blink green LED on IR detection	☐	disabled

Bluetooth

Interval for Bluetooth inquiries (used for BT detections)	<input type="range"/>	25000ms
Random value to +- BT inquiry interval, e.g. value of 1000 means actual detections happen (interval +- 1000 ms)	<input type="range"/>	5000ms
Blink blue LED on BT detection	☐	disabled
The maximum amount of time before the BT inquiry process is halted. Must be less than inquiry interval	<input type="range"/>	5120ms
Limit Bluetooth detections only to Sociometric Badges	☒	enabled
BT power setting for responding to inquiries	<input type="range"/>	4dB
BT power setting for maximum power	<input type="range"/>	4dB
BT power setting for sending inquiries	<input type="range"/>	4dB

Audio

Audio data to skip on start	<input type="range"/>	10s
Audio sensitivity	<input type="range"/>	3x
Channels	<input type="range"/>	2ch

Audio features (back)

Feature storage interval	<input type="range"/>	100ms
Save Mel bands	☐	disabled
Save spectrum	☐	disabled
Save cepstrum	☐	disabled

Audio features (front)

Feature storage interval	<input type="range"/>	100ms
Save Mel bands	☐	disabled
Save spectrum	☐	disabled
Save cepstrum	☐	disabled

Audio features (differential)

Raw audio storage

Fast features storage

Slow features storage

Fast features storage (encrypted)

Slow features storage (encrypted)

SQLite storage

USB connection management

SD card management

Logging

Power management

Real time clock

Charge interval	<input type="range"/>	15days
Charge time	<input type="range"/>	6hours
Synchronize system time from RTC	☒	enabled